

Supplementary Information

An update on micro- and nanoplastics in foods from plastic food contact articles: Protocol for a systematic evidence map

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Search string development

We will search for published studies on MNP present in foods or food simulants, potentially originating from FCAs, that were published after December 14, 2022. An effective search strategy will identify as many relevant studies as possible while minimizing the retrieval of irrelevant studies and screening efforts. Our main reason for keeping the screening burden low is to enable regular updates of the FCMiNo database while minimizing time requirements, even though we anticipate a significant increase in the volume of published literature on the topic. In FCMiNo_v1, we identified 5979 potentially relevant studies, from which data were extracted for only 1.72% (103 studies; Zimmermann et al., 2025). To develop a more targeted search string, we used the 103 studies included in FCMiNo_v1 as a benchmark. As a first approach (A), we constructed an initial search string based on the titles of these benchmark studies. Through an iterative process, we tested and refined the string for each database, evaluating its specificity and sensitivity based on the following criteria:

- 26 • **Screening burden:** How many studies do we need to screen to achieve satisfactory
27 completeness?
- 28 • **Relevance:** Do we retrieve benchmark studies, previously identified in the same or a different
29 database?
- 30 • **High relevance:** Do we successfully retrieve benchmark studies that had previously been
31 appraised as highly relevant?

32 Using approach A, we were able to reduce the screening burden, but at the cost of missing relevant
33 and highly relevant studies. For instance, in WoS, after several rounds of optimization, we reduced the
34 number of studies to screen compared to FCMiNo_v1 by 80%. However, we identified only 80% of
35 the benchmark references previously found in WoS (68 out of 85) and four of the seven highly
36 relevant studies. As an alternative, approach B involved rebuilding our search string based on the one
37 used in FCMiNo_v1, even though this may increase the screening burden. Specifically, we added
38 further food and beverage categories (*e.g.*, tofu, oil) and FCAs (*e.g.*, transport equipment, chopping
39 board, kettle). We also kept the search group related to ‘particle’ more generic, avoiding specific
40 polymer types, preventing bias toward certain polymers while neglecting others (Zimmermann et al.,
41 2025). We then tested different combinations of the search groups developed in approaches A and B.
42 The outcome was that adding a search group related to ‘particle NEAT process/generic foodstuff’
43 (part of approach B) to our adapted search string from FCMiNo_v1 using an OR Boolean operator
44 (Table 2) allowed us to identify additional highly relevant studies. By combining approaches A and B
45 in this way, we achieved a balance between reducing the screening burden and identifying all highly
46 relevant and nearly all relevant studies. For instance, in WoS, we identify 98% (83 out of 85) of the
47 studies previously identified in this database, all seven highly relevant studies, and reduce screening
48 by 30% compared to FCMiNo_v1. Notably, the optimized search string also identifies benchmark
49 studies not previously retrieved in the respective literature database (*e.g.*, 6 in the case of WoS), along
50 with additional potentially relevant studies not included in FCMiNo_v1. In FCMiNo_v1, 85 of the
51 103 included studies were found in WoS (Figure S1). With the new search string, 89 of the 103 are
52 identified with WoS.

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55 **Figure S1.** Number of benchmark studies identified in FCMiNo_v1 per database consulted. Besides Web of
 56 Science, PubMed, and ScienceDirect, we included references from relevant reports (“Reports”) and the Database
 57 on Migrating and Extractable Food Contact Chemicals (“FCCmigex”), containing the terms “microplastic(s)”,
 58 “nanoplastic(s)”, or “plastic particle(s)” in the title.

59 ScienceDirect limits the number of search terms that can be used, allowing, for example, a maximum
 60 of eight terms in full-text searches. As a result, a simplified version of the search string was developed
 61 and optimized separately for this database. The optimized search string reduces the number of studies
 62 to screen by approximately 76% compared to the FCMiNo_v1 search string. Yet, it still identifies 88%
 63 of the benchmark studies previously retrieved from ScienceDirect, along with three additional
 64 benchmark studies not previously identified in this database. In FCMiNo_v1, we also gathered
 65 additional references from key reports (“backward snowballing”), and included all references from the
 66 Database on Migrating and Extractable Food Contact Chemicals (FCCmigex) with the terms
 67 “microplastic(s)”, “nanoplastic(s)”, or “plastic particle(s)” in the title (Geueke et al., 2023). As Figure
 68 S1 illustrates, all references identified in FCCmigex were also found in at least one other source.
 69 Therefore, we will not search that database for references in version 2. However, we will continue to
 70 gather references from relevant reports published since 2 of the 103 studies included in FCMiNo_v1
 71 were only identified through evaluated reports.

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73 **References**

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